

The Enhanced Cytotoxic Effect of

Ganoderma Lucidum Polysaccharide Nanoparticles Across Various Cancer Cell Lines

Yugandhar Parepalli ^{1,2}, Devaraju. S ^{1, *}, Mahalakshmi C.S. Parepalli ³

¹ *Polymer Composites Lab, Department of Chemistry, School of Applied Science and Humanities, Vignan's Foundation for Science, Technology and Research (Deemed to be University), Vadlamudi, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA.*

² *Discovery Analytical department, Eurofins Advinus Discovery Services Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.*

³ *Department of Pharmaceutical chemistry, G. Pulla Reddy College of Pharmacy, Mehdipatnam, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.*

* Correspondence:

S. Devaraju

Polymer Composites Lab, Department of Chemistry, Vignan University, Vadlamudi, Guntur, 522213, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA.

ABSTRACT:

Health benefits of plants and other living organisms from nature have been studied since ages in particular in the form of traditional medicine. Modern day research has been more focusing the underlying scientific reasons behind these health benefits. Ganoderma lucidum is one such fungi that has known for its immense benefits like antioxidant, antibacterial, controlling blood glucose levels and having immunoregulatory properties and so on. In this regard, we have isolated Ganoderma polysaccharides and studied the anti-cancer activities. Ganoderma polysaccharides possess good anti-cancer activity at relatively higher concentrations. To check the anticancer activity, with low concentration polysaccharides were loaded in to chitosan nanoparticles and studied their size and loading efficiency. The free polysaccharides and polysaccharide loaded nanoparticles were evaluated for cytotoxic activity on various human cancer cell lines like breast, ovarian and hepatocellular cancers by MTT assay. The results obtained from MTT assay suggested a significant reduction in the IC_{50} concentration of polysaccharide loaded nanoparticles compared to free polysaccharide.

Key words: Ganoderma lucidum, Polysaccharides, Nanoparticles, Anti-cancer, Cytotoxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Plants, animal and other biological species on this earth have and are playing a key role for the successful existence of man since time immemorial. These living systems as a whole or as component play a key role in the development and well-being of the mankind. Many of such species have been recorded by the ancestors traditionally for their food and medicinal value. One such species is *Ganoderma lucidum* (*G lucidum*) which has been used as Chinese medicinal material since ages.¹ Recent research revealed the major bioactive component of *G lucidum* to be its polysaccharides.² In addition to polysaccharides, it also contains wide variety of triterpenoids, glycoprotein's, meroterpenoids, alkaloids, benzoic acid derivatives, sesquiterpenoids and steroids along with minerals like Zinc, calcium, magnesium, potassium, iron, phosphorus and selenium.³ The percentage composition of above constituents from *G lucidum* is mainly dependent on use of polar and nonpolar solvents for the extraction process. The major components of extraction obtained with either polar or nonpolar solvents are polysaccharides and triterpenes respectively.⁴

G lucidum polysaccharides (GLPs) are mainly composed of glycoproteins, polysaccharides and (1→3), (1→6)- α/β -glucans.⁵ GLPs demonstrate diverse biological properties like antioxidant, controlling blood glucose levels, antibacterial and immunoregulatory properties.⁶ GLPs are proven for their safety and non-toxicity which is the major reason behind their use in cosmetics, food and many other medicinal products.⁷ Recent research on GLPs, established their anti-tumor activities against few cancer lines. For example, GLPs have exhibited evident inhibitory effects in breast cancer, colon cancer cell lines.² These anti-tumor attributes of GLPs are supposed to be strongly linked to their biological processes regulating ability, like immune and inflammatory responses and also inducing cytotoxicity in tumor cells, by enhancing the apoptosis.⁸ These are also known to inhibit metastasis and boost the immune system of the patients with their immunomodulatory property.

The major drawback of this *G lucidum* in terms of its anti-tumor activity is the concentration of the compound required to elicit cytotoxicity.⁹ Literature survey reveals that Ganopoly® a commercial *G lucidum* extract is active at concentration of 10 mg/ml¹⁰, and another product ReishiMax GLp® is active at

1mg/ml concentration.^{2,11} Taking in to account of all the above points we hypothesize that formulating these GLPs in to chitosan nanoparticles would help in reducing the concentration of the compound required for anti-tumor effect. Chitosan polymeric nanoparticles were chosen for delivery of GLPs in view of their biocompatibility and nontoxic nature. In addition, the pH responsive nature of chitosan nanoparticles can also be exploited to harness the maximum efficacy of these GLPs through site specific delivery. Nanoparticulate delivery system in specific helps in effectively delivering the GLPs at tumorigenic cells site and efficiently loading the hydrophilic GLPs. To realize the hypothesis, we have formulated the GLP loaded chitosan nanoparticles-a biocompatible carbohydrate polymer, and evaluated the cytotoxic effect of both free GLPs and GLP nanoparticles on various cancer cell lines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ganoderma mushroom and Chitosan we purchased from the S Agrotech, Kukatpally Hyderabad. DMEM (Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium), MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide], Sodium Tripolyphosphate (TPP), trypsin, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), DMSO and Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Fetal bovine serum (FBS) was purchased from Gibco. 25 cm² and 75 cm² flask and 96 well plates were acquired from Eppendorf India.

METHODOLOGY:

Nanoparticle Formulation:

Chitosan-GLP nanoparticles were prepared by adding 10 ml GLP solution to the chitosan solution (2.5mg/ml; 100ml) which was prepared by dissolving chitosan in 1 % (v/v) acetic acid aqueous solution for one hour under magnetic stirring. Then 1 M NaOH solution used to adjust the pH of the reaction solution to 5.0 and the solution was stirred for one hour at room temperature. Finally, counter ion TPP solution (1 mg/ml in distilled water) was added to chitosan-GLP solution under mild magnetic stirring at 70 rpm for 1 h to form the chitosan-GLP nanoparticles. Then the solution was centrifuged at 22000 rpm at

4°C for 30 mins, after discarding the supernatant, the nanoparticles at the bottom were collected, washed with water and finally lyophilized at -97°C using trehalose as cryoprotectant and used for further studies.¹²

CHARACTERIZATION:

Particle Size: Particle size analysis was performed by dynamic light scattering (DLS-Malvern-UK). DLS determines the mean diameter and the polydispersity index (PI) which is a measure of the width of the size distribution. The mean diameter and PI values were obtained at an angle of 90° in 10 mm diameter cells at 25°C. Prior to the measurements 100µl of all samples were diluted with 900µl double distilled water to produce a suitable scattering intensity.

Scanning Electron Microscopy: SEM (FESEM, JEOL JSM-7610F) was used to determine the size and morphology of the nanoparticles formulated. Lyophilized samples were placed under the microscope and images were captured at different resolutions.

Loading Efficiency: The quantity of GLP entrapped in the nanoparticles was calculated by the Diethylamino ethyl cellulose DEAE weak anion exchange method. DEAE-C is a weak anion exchanger. This exchange is utilized to separate proteins that have faintly differing charges. Like all anion exchangers, the resin carries a positive charge that interacts favorably with negative charges. The positive charge of DEAE cellulose is due to a protonated amine group. GLP loading capacity was calculated as,

$$\text{Loading Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total GLP} - \text{Free GLP}}{\text{Weight of Nanoparticles}}$$

MAINTENANCE AND CULTURE OF CELL LINE:

The cancer cell lines MCF-7, HeLa, HepG2 were purchased from NCCS, Pune and were maintained in Dulbecco's modified eagle (DMEM) media supplemented with 10 % FBS and the antibiotics penicillin/streptomycin (0.5 mL⁻¹), in atmosphere of 5% CO₂/95% air at 37⁰ C.

CYTOTOXICITY ASSAY:

Cell viability of the polysaccharide and the nanoparticles was determined using MTT assay with three independent experiments with six concentrations of compounds in triplicates. Cells were trypsinized at confluence and viability was determined using trypan blue assay. Cells were counted on a hemocytometer and seeded at density of 5.0×10^3 cells / well in 100 μ l media in 96 well plate culture medium and incubated overnight at 37⁰ C. After incubation, old media was replaced with fresh media (100 μ l) containing different concentrations of test compounds GLP and GLP nanoparticles (5, 10, 25, 50 and 100 μ g) were added to wells in 96 plates. After 48 hrs. incubation the supernatant was discarded and fresh media containing MTT solution (0.5 mg / mL⁻¹) was added to each well and plates were incubated at 37⁰ C for 3 hrs. At the end of incubation period DMSO was added to wells, as a result of which precipitates are formed due to the reduction of the MTT salt to chromophore formazan crystals by the cells with metabolically active mitochondria. The optical density of solubilized crystals in DMSO was measured at 570 nm on a microplate reader. The percentage growth inhibition was calculated using the following formula.¹³

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 * \frac{(\text{Control} - \text{Treatment})}{\text{Control}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GLP loaded chitosan nanoparticles were formulated and characterized for their size and loading efficiency. Chitosan was selected as bio-polymer for loading the GLP and formulating nanoparticles owing to its biodegradability and non-toxic nature. The bi products of the polymer degradation are proven to be non-toxic and most important nature of this polymer is its pH responsive nature, where in acidic pH the polymer swells and vice versa with alkaline pH¹⁴ This nature of the polymer can be very well exploited for our present research so that the GLP can directly be release in the acidic environment of the cancerous cells but not elsewhere targeted delivery. The primary amines of the polymer in acidic environment leads to withdrawal of protons from cytoplasm and create an osmotic imbalance in the cells, which leads to

expulsion of the pay load in cell microenvironment. From the data obtained the size of the nanoparticles was found to be 100 nm (Figure 1) and LE was found to be 82%. SEM was performed to characterize and analyze the surface morphology, size distribution and to determine the presence of any agglomerates in the final optimized formulated nanoparticles. From images in Figure 2, 3 of the nanoparticles reveal the spherical morphology of the nanoparticles at 100nm scale and no agglomerates were observed when zoomed at 1 μ m scale.

1)

2)

3)

Fig.1 Particle size graph of the final optimized nanoparticles; SEM images of GLP loaded chitosan nanoparticles 2) low magnification (1 μ m) and 3) at high magnification (100nm)

The GLP and GLP loaded nanoparticles cytotoxicity was evaluated by adding them to the cancer cell lines plated in 96 well plate and incubated for 48 hrs. then after the viability determined using MTT assay. From the Table 1 and Figure 2 clearly seen that a significant reduction in the IC₅₀ values of free GLPs and GLP loaded nanoparticles in all the three cell lines. The free GLPs show the IC₅₀ of 72.9, 71.0 and 65.3 µg for MCF-7, HeLa and HepG₂ cell lines respectively. Whereas the GLP loaded nanoparticles have elicited 50% inhibition of the cells at a very lower concentration of 18.9, 17.6 and 15.9 µg which were very much comparable with the standard cisplatin. From the above data it is evident that the GLP loaded nanoparticles had a potent cytotoxic effect at lower concentrations than the free GLP. This cytotoxic effect of the loaded nanoparticles may be attributed to their site specific release of the GLPs, as chitosan polymer has a tendency to swell in acidic conditions, the acidic microenvironment of the cancerous cell might have triggered the release of GLPs in cytoplasm of the cell, whereas the free GLPs could not have reached the cytoplasm in sufficient concentration to cause the cell lysis as they may have got degraded in the acidic environment of the cancer cell rendering them inactive or partially active components.^{15, 16}

Table No.1

IC₅₀^a values of GLP and GLP loaded nanoparticles.

S. No	Sample name	IC ₅₀ (µg)		
		MCF 7	HeLa	HepG ₂
1	GLP	72.95±0.652	71.06±0.719	65.34±0.252
2	GLP nanoparticles	18.90±0.652	17.64±0.719	15.92±0.252
3	*Cisplatin	1.69 ± 0.141	2.26±0.257	3.5±0.183

^aIC₅₀ values are expressed as mean ±SD (n = 3), *reference sample.

Fig.2 IC₅₀ values of GLP, GLP nanoparticles along with standard Cisplatin. All the values obtained were average of triplicates from three individual experiments. * = P < 0.05, calculated using students T test between GLP and GLP nanoparticles.

In addition to determination of IC₅₀ values we have also captured the optical images of cell lines treated with GLP loaded nanoparticle using microscope at 40X magnification. From the Figure-3 it's evident that the % cell viability has reduced drastically as the concentration of the nanoparticles has increased (5, 10, 25 and 100 µg) respectively. In the first concentration of all the three cell lines MCF, HeLa and HepG2 a densely populated surface can be viewed, as the concentration increased gradually visible lacuna in the cells can be observed. This decrease in cell density is due to mortality of the cells upon treating with the GLP loaded nanoparticles which is clearly visible with change in cell morphology. From the above assay inference, we can conclude the cytotoxicity nature of GLP loaded nanoparticles which supports the IC₅₀ values obtained from MTT assay.

A)

MCF 7

5µg

10µg

25µg

50µg

100µg

B)

C)

Fig.3 Microscopic images of MCF-7 cells, B) HeLa cells, C) HepG₂ cells after treatment with GLP loaded nanoparticles at various concentrations of 5, 10, 25, 50 and 100 µg.

From the above *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay, it is clearly evident that the GLP loaded nanoparticles are having a higher cytotoxic effect on cancerous cell lines in comparison to the free GLPs. This data supports our hypothesis of formulating the GLPs in to nanoparticles for an effective cytotoxic effect on cancer cell lines. This research work also gives us a clue regarding the combinatorial delivery of cancer drugs for effective tumor regression using the nanoparticles.

CONCLUSION

In this work we have synthesized GLP loaded nanoparticles and studied the cytotoxic effect and compared with free GLP. The size of synthesized GLP nanoparticle was about 100 nm from SEM and particle size analyzer. The GLP loaded into chitosan nanoparticle showed better cytotoxic ability than the free GLP against breast, ovarian and hepatocellular cancer cell lines by *in vitro* MTT assay. The GLP loaded nanoparticle showed good activity (50% inhibition) at lower concentration (15-18 μg) than the free GLP (65-72 μg). This may be attributed to site specific release of the GLP with help of nanoparticles where in the maximum number of polysaccharides can come in to action without getting degraded in acidic environment. This hypothesis can be supported with the data obtained for free GLPs which shows that almost three times of the concentration is required to show same 50% inhibition, which may be attributed to the acidic degradation of the polysaccharides rendering it to be less active or may be in active.

STATISTICS

A students T test was run using software to compare the significance level of IC_{50} values between GLP and GLP nanoparticles. A p value ≤ 0.05 is considered as statistically significant.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to Vignan's University, Guntur for providing laboratory facilities.

REFERENCES:

- 1 Wachtel-Galor S, Tomlinson B, Benzie IFF. *Ganoderma lucidum* ("Lingzhi"), a Chinese medicinal mushroom: biomarker responses in a controlled human supplementation study. *Br J Nutr.* 2004 Feb;91(2):263-9
- 2 Sohretoglu D, Huang S. *Ganoderma lucidum* polysaccharides as an anti-cancer agent. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem.* 2018; 18(5): 667–674.
- 3 Cör D, Knez Ž, Hrnčič MK. *Antitumour, antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-acetylcholinesterase effect of Ganoderma lucidum terpenoids and polysaccharides: A Review. Molecules.* 2018 Mar 13;23(3):649.
- 4 Traversier M, Gaslondes T, Milesi S, Michel S, Delannay E. *Polar lipids in cosmetics: recent trends in extraction, separation, analysis and main applications. Phytochemistry Reviews,* 2018, № 5, 1179-1210.
- 5 Ferreira ICFR, Heleno SA, Reis FS, Stojkovic D, Queiroz MJRP, Vasconcelos MH, et al. *Chemical features of Ganoderma polysaccharides with antioxidant, antitumor and antimicrobial activities. Phytochemistry.* 2015 Jun; 114:38-55.
- 6 Ahmad, MF. *Ganoderma lucidum: Persuasive biologically active constituents and their health endorsement. Biomed Pharmacother.* 2018 Nov: 107:507-519.
- 7 Ahmad R, Riaz M, Khan A, Aljamea A, Algheryafi M, Sewaket D, et al. *Ganoderma lucidum (Reishi) an edible mushroom; a comprehensive and critical review of its nutritional, cosmeceutical, mycochemical, pharmacological, clinical, and toxicological properties. Phytother Res.* 2021 Nov;35(11):6030-6062.
- 8 Meng X, Liang H, Luo L. *Antitumor polysaccharides from mushrooms: a review on the structural characteristics, antitumor mechanisms and immunomodulating activities. Carbohydr Res.* 2016 Apr 7:424:30-41
- 9 Kim HS, Kacew S, Lee BM. *In vitro chemopreventive effects of plant polysaccharides (Aloe barbadensis miller, Lentinus edodes, Ganoderma lucidum and Coriolus versicolor). Carcinogenesis.* 1999 Aug;20(8):1637-40
- 10 Gao Y, Gao H, Chan E, Tang W, Xu A, Yang H, et al. *Antitumor activity and underlying mechanisms of ganopoly, the refined polysaccharides extracted from Ganoderma lucidum, in mice. Immunol Invest.* 2005;34(2):171-98.
- 11 Sohretoglu D, Zhang C, Luo J & Huang S. *ReishiMax inhibits mTORC1/2 by activating AMPK and inhibiting IGFR/PI3K/Rheb in tumor cells. Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy volume 4, Article number: 21 (2019)*
- 12 Parepalli Y, Chavali M, sami R, Khojah E. *Evaluation of Some Active Nutrients, Biological Compounds and Health Benefits of Reishi Mushroom (Ganoderma lucidum). Int. J. Pharmacol.* 2021. 17(4):243-250.
- 13 Solipeta DR, Siva B, Vemulapalli S, Pallavi PMC. *Secophragmalin-type limonoids from Trichilia connaroides: isolation, semisynthesis, and their cytotoxic activities. J.Nat. Prod.* 2019. 82(10):2731-2743.
- 14 Rizwan M, Yahya R, Hassan A, Yar M, Azzahari AD, Selvanathan V, et al. *pH Sensitive Hydrogels in Drug Delivery: Brief History, Properties, Swelling, and Release Mechanism, Material Selection and Applications. Polymers (Basel).* 2017 Apr; 9(4): 137.
- 15 Zheng D, Zhao J, Yinghua, T, Liu J. *pH and glutathione dual responsive nanoparticles based on Ganoderma lucidum polysaccharide for potential programmable release of three drugs. J. Chem. Eng.* 2020 Jun. 389:124418.
- 16 Shao P, Xuan S, Wu W, Qu L. *Encapsulation efficiency and controlled release of Ganoderma lucidum polysaccharide microcapsules by spray drying using different combinations of wall materials. Int J Biol Macromol.* 2019 Mar 15:125:962-969